

Nature-based solutions for wastewater treatment: Biodegradable freeze-dried powdered bio-flocculant

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ABSTRACT

A significant problem concerning the utilisation of nature-based coagulants (or biocoagulants) in practice and for commercialisation, is their stability (i.e., of their active components) and durability over long periods. In this context, a powdered biocoagulant was produced from common bean seeds (*Phaseolus vulgaris*) by extraction and freeze-drying and then tested for its stability and durability. Four powdered biocoagulants were tested and compared in terms of their coagulation activity, hygroscopicity, water solubility and moisture content. All 4 maintained high efficiency for turbidity removal (50.6–80.2 %) despite and during several months of storage (in both controlled and non-controlled conditions). Similarly, these biocoagulants had low hygroscopicity (between 7.6 and 8.5 g of water per 100 g of sample), moisture content (< 8 g per 100 g of sample) and high water solubility indices (between 88.0 and 92.7 % and between 62.6 and 78.1 % for salt and distilled water extracts, respectively) with a low coefficient of variation (< 5 %) during the testing period and within repeated experiments. Biocoagulants extracted with 0.5 M salt solution showed better results in terms of their tested physico-chemical properties. However, biocoagulants extracted by ultrasound extraction using distilled water as a solvent showed the highest consistency in terms of optimal coagulant dosage and achieved turbidity removal. Instrumental characterisation through SEM/EDX, FTIR, XRD and XPS analysis were included for the coagulant with the best consistency in coagulation activity over the time. Biocoagulants were also tested using lake water and several types of industrial wastewater (i.e., from a whisky distillery and a meat processing plant) and showed good potential for organic matter reduction even in real (complex) environmental matrices.

1. Introduction

Water industries recognise coagulation/flocculation (CF) as one of the major treatment processes available within water and wastewater treatment [1]. CF can subsequently affect downstream processes such as settling/flotation, filtration, adsorption, oxidation and disinfection [1]. Removal of colloidal and suspended particles by CF is usually achieved with commercial coagulants based on ferrous (FeCl₃, FeSO₄) or aluminium salts (Al₂(SO₄)₃, AlCl₃), as well as different organic polymers and flocculants such as acrylamide, acrylic acid and polyacrylamide [2]. However, due to toxicity related risks (e.g., Al may promote the development of Alzheimer's; [3], and other hazards connected with synthetic coagulants/flocculants (i.e., residues remaining in discharged water and/or the production of non-biodegradable toxic sludge), there are

calls to replace such materials with more environmentally friendly coagulants of a biological origin (here, 'biocoagulants').

These coagulants can be produced from animals (chitin), plants (seeds/pods, leaves, mucilage, wastes, etc.) or microorganisms (bacteria, fungi and algae), however biocoagulants extracted from plants (such as *Moringa oleifera*, cactus, bean, okra, mango, banana, etc.) are most commonly investigated [2,4,5]. These tend to be safer, biodegradable, sustainable, highly available/abundant, produce less sludge [4] and they are relatively cost-efficient (i.e., in terms of sludge handling and biocoagulant costs) [6]. In comparison to *Moringa oleifera* material (which is widely studied), bean seeds don't contain oils and no extraction with organic solvents (e.g., alcohol) is necessary to produce a biocoagulant - which is then beneficial from an economic and sustainability perspective [7]. Proteins (amino acids) and carbohydrates

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(polysaccharides) are the main active components of such biocoagulants [4]. As these natural materials are by their nature highly biodegradable, their shelf-life also has to be considered [2]. Shelf-life is a common problem with certain coagulants kept in their liquid forms, which are often not stable over long periods of time and require special storage in refrigerators/freezers [8] (to preserve their activity). In order to extend shelf-life and make such materials more commercially attractive, liquid extracts are often converted into a powdered form. For this, different drying techniques can be utilised (i.e., spray drying, vacuum drying, freeze-drying and spouted bed drying) [9], of which the most common are lyophilisation (freeze-drying) and spray drying.

To date, several studies have shown the effects of these drying techniques on biocoagulant properties, mainly using *Moringa oleifera* based materials [8,10–12]. While spray dried biocoagulants from *Moringa oleifera* have shown good results in terms of coagulation efficiency [10,13], lyophilisation has benefits in preserving heat-labile components such as proteins [14]. However, there is a limited research into lyophilisation in terms of its efficiency in protecting proteins in *Moringa oleifera* extracts [10,12,15]. Katayon et al. (2006) proved that a freeze-dried biocoagulant from *Moringa oleifera* retained high coagulation efficiency, even after 11 months of storage. Zheng et al. (2021) studied biocoagulants obtained from *Hibiscus sabdariffa*, and plant powders were compared directly with freeze-dried plant extracts in terms of dye removal from wastewater. Coagulants obtained using lyophilisation gave better results, not only in terms of dye removal (due to preserved protein content), but also in terms of surface morphology (higher porosity), solubility and reduced water activity (water activity was <0.6, which prevented microorganism growth and thus decomposition of the protein content) [16].

Most papers on biocoagulant utilisation for water/wastewater treatment focus on a reduction in certain water quality parameters. However, few articles have compared the production of powdered biocoagulants (using different drying technologies) and investigated their impact on the physico-chemical stability of different materials over time. To start to fill this knowledge gap and provide a more complete picture that is relevant to biocoagulant commercialisation, we present research regarding both coagulation ability (and thus reduction in turbidity and organic matter) alongside key biocoagulant characteristics (i.e., hygroscopicity, water solubility, moisture and dry matter content) for freeze-dried plant-based biocoagulants (made from common bean seeds) – and consider biocoagulant preservation (in terms of desired functionality) over several months using different storage conditions. This study considers multiple important key aspects that need to be understood if such materials are to become commercially available products (wherein stability and durability are critical). The need for investigation of practical applicability of biocoagulants was highlighted in different review articles [6,17,18]. Furthermore, we observe changes in Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) when using these biocoagulants - as this is an important knowledge gap in research on biocoagulants [19]. This paper considers COD increases/decreases with the addition of biocoagulants in different water/wastewater matrices.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials and biocoagulant production

The natural material used for biocoagulant production was common bean seeds (*Phaseolus vulgaris*) purchased from a local market and stored in dry, room temperature conditions before further processing.

A simple, three step production processes included grinding and screening, extraction and drying [20]. First, bean seeds were ground in a mechanical mill and sieved to <0.4 mm. The resultant fine powder was used for further processing. Two types of extraction were conducted, a conventional solid/liquid extraction and an ultrasound extraction - both with two different types of solvent (distilled water and 0.5 M NaCl solution). Prior to extraction, bean suspensions were prepared by

suspending at a ratio of 1/20 powder/extraction agent. For conventional solid/liquid extraction, the suspension was stirred for 10 min on a magnetic stirrer [7]. For ultrasound extraction, the ultrasound frequency used was 40 kHz for 50 min at 25 °C (when NaCl was the solvent) and 40 kHz for 45 min at 42 °C (when distilled water was used). The optimal extraction conditions were determined experimentally (unpublished data). After extraction, suspensions were filtered through a filter paper (Macherey-Nagel, MN 651/120) in order to obtain crude extracts of active components. Before the final stage (drying) the crude extracts were put in a freezer overnight. Frozen extracts were then lyophilised in a freeze dryer (Alpha 1–2 LDplus, Martin Christ Gefrier-trocknungsanlagen GmbH, Germany) under vacuum at 0.07 mbar and at –45 °C for 48 h. Ultimately, 4 different powdered coagulants were obtained and denoted as: KVO (conventional solid/liquid extraction with distilled water), KNO (conventional solid/liquid extraction with NaCl solution), UVO (ultrasound extraction with distilled water) and UNO (ultrasound extraction with NaCl solution). A simplified production schematic is given in Fig. 1.

The obtained powdered biocoagulants were then kept in the dark (in plastic containers) in controlled (reduced moisture conditions achieved by keeping samples in the desiccator) and non-controlled conditions (at room temperature) for 4 and 6 months, respectively. The dynamics of coagulation for each powder were checked after 0 months (before storage), and after 2 and 4 months from production for controlled storage; and after 0 months (before storage), 1.5, 3 and 6 months from production for non-controlled conditions. The characteristics of all 8 coagulants were simultaneously followed and compared in order to indicate the best option for further testing and scale-up.

2.2. Hygroscopicity

Hygroscopicity was determined based on a slightly modified method after Vladić et al. (2016) [9] and Goula and Adamopoulos (2010) [21]. Approximately 1 g of each powder was placed in a separate petri dish and then into a desiccator containing saturated NaCl solution (70 % relative humidity). Hygroscopicity was calculated by the difference in powder weight after a certain time period (12 h, 1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 days) spent in the humid environment and finally expressed as g of absorbed water per 100 g of coagulant.

2.3. Water solubility index (WSI)

WSI was determined according to the methods previously published by Phoungchandang and Sertwasana, (2010) and Vladić et al. (2016). Briefly, 1.5 g of biocoagulant powder and 15 mL of water were mixed vigorously in a 50 mL centrifuge tube. The mixture was incubated in a water bath at 30 °C for 30 min and centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 min. Pre-weighted petri dishes were used to collect the supernatant (after centrifugation) and these were put in an oven to dry at 105 °C overnight. Samples were cooled in a desiccator and then weighed. The mass of dried supernatant as a proportion of the initial mass of powdered coagulant indicated its water solubility index - expressed as a percentage [9].

2.4. Moisture and dry matter content

The moisture content in dry extracts was determined gravimetrically from the difference in mass of dry extract before and after drying at 105 °C until constant mass [9]. The following equation was used for the calculation of the moisture content:

$$\text{Moisture content} = \frac{m_1 - m_2}{m_1} \times 100 (\%) \quad (1)$$

where m_1 and m_2 (g) represent the powder mass before and after drying to constant mass, respectively. Consequently, the dry matter content (%)

Fig. 1. Bio-coagulant production schematic (simplified).

of the powdered biocoagulant was calculated as 100 % - moisture content (%).

The dry matter content of liquid extracts was determined by taking 5 mL of the liquid (in a glass round bottom flask), weighing this, evaporating in a lab evaporator, and then drying in an oven at 105 °C for 2.5 h. The dry matter content was calculated from the difference in weight of the flask with dried sample and the flask without sample. Dry matter was expressed in g of dry matter per L of liquid coagulant.

2.5. Model water and real water/wastewater

Model water used in all experiments had an initial turbidity of 200 nephelometric turbidity units (NTU) and was pH 6. The desired turbidity was achieved by preparing a 1 % kaolin suspension in tap water, just before the coagulation experiments. To prepare the 1 % kaolin suspension, 10 g of kaolin was added to 1 L of tap water and mixed using a magnetic stirrer (for 1 h). Mixed suspensions were poured into dark glassware and left for 24 h to achieve complete hydration of particles [5]. The initial pH of the model water was adjusted with the addition of HCl, just before experiments.

Lake water, whisky distillery effluent and effluent from a meat processing plant were collected and kept in a refrigerator until use. Their initial pH, turbidity and COD values are listed in Table 1.

2.6. Jar-test experiments

Before conducting jar-test experiments, powdered coagulants were returned from their powdered into liquid form, which was done by simple suspension of certain amount of powdered biocoagulant (0.1915, 0.4723, 0.1716 or 0.4614 g of KVO, KNO, UVO and UNO biocoagulant, respectively) into 10 mL of distilled water. Once suspended in an appropriate ratio (Table 2), powders and distilled water were moderately stirred for 10 mins on a magnetic stirrer before use in jar test experiments.

Coagulation activity was determined using jar test experiments. Different doses of biocoagulants (from 0.05 to 1.5 mL/L) were added during fast mixing to 600 mL beakers containing 200 mL of model water or real water/wastewater. Model water or real water/wastewater mixed without a coagulant created a blank sample. Samples were first mixed

Table 1
Initial properties of real water/wastewater samples.

Type of water	Initial pH	Turbidity (NTU)	COD (mg/L)
Lake water (LW), Scotland	7.3	4.3	27.1
Whisky distillery effluent (WDE), Scotland	3.9	9400	150
Meat processing effluent (EMCI), Serbia	2	256	2705

Table 2
Dry matter contents in liquid extracts of common bean seeds.

Coagulant type	Dry matter in liquid extracts (g/L)	STDV
KVO	19.15	0.52
KNO	47.23	2.39
UVO	17.16	0.03
UNO	46.14	0.62

fast (200 rpm) for 1 min, then slowly (60 rpm) for the next 30 mins and finally left to settle for 1 h. After 1 h of sedimentation, the upper clarified liquid was collected and its residual turbidity and/or organic matter content were determined.

Coagulation activity (CA) was expressed as turbidity removal or organic matter removal. Coagulation activity (%) was calculated using the following equation:

$$\text{Coagulation activity} = \frac{(C_b - C_s)}{C_b} \times 100 (\%) \quad (2)$$

where C_b and C_s represent turbidity (NTU) or organic matter content (mg/L) of the blank and the samples, respectively.

2.7. Analytical methods and instrumental characterisation

Turbidity was measured using a turbidimeter (WTW TURB 550/550 IR). Organic matter content was determined as chemical oxygen demand (COD) according to Standard Methods [23]. pH was measured before and after coagulation using a pH meter (Oakton Ion 6). All experiments were conducted in duplicate and the mean value with standard deviation was presented.

SEM/EDX (JEOL JSM-7800-F, Japan) was used in order to examine surface morphology and elemental composition of biocoagulant, while crystalline/amorphous structure of biocoagulant was confirmed using XRD (D2 Phaser diffractometer, Bruker, Germany). FTIR spectroscopy was used in order to determine functional groups present on the biocoagulant. FTIR spectra were recorded in the range from 600 to 4000 cm^{-1} with 2 cm^{-1} resolution (Nexus 670, Thermo Nicolet, USA). XPS (Thermo Scientific K-Alpha XPS spectrometer, UK) was used for analysis of composition and speciation of biocoagulant surface elements.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Hygroscopicity

Hygroscopicity represents a powders ability to absorb ambient moisture [24]. Hence, it is an important parameter which should be investigated in potential commercial products such as biocoagulants. Different hydrophilic compounds, including proteins, commonly found in herbal extracts, can cause high hygroscopicity [25]. However, lower

hygroscopicity is preferable as a higher ability to absorb moisture can lead to undesirable caking [26], which can affect coagulation of the powder in water or hinder powder solubility [12].

Fig. 2 shows the hygroscopicity of common bean seed biocoagulants. It can be noted that the maximum hygroscopicity values were all <9 g of water per 100 g of powdered biocoagulant. These results are comparable to those for other freeze-dried natural products such as yellow mombin pulp powder, which had a hygroscopicity (without and with the addition of maltodextrin) of 12.93 and 8.51 %, respectively [27]. Similar results were also observed for Moringa (*Moringa oleifera* Lam) leaf juice powder (11 g of water per 100 g of powder) [28]. In contrast, Silva et al. (2019) reported the hygroscopicity of freeze-dried *Moringa oleifera* coagulant to be 95.1 %. Here, lower hygroscopicity was observed for biocoagulants extracted with salt solution as compared to those extracted with distilled water. In this sense, the KNO and UNO biocoagulants were of slightly higher quality than the KVO and UVO materials. As indicated by Oliveira et al. (2014) the hygroscopicity of freeze-dried products can be further decreased by the addition of materials such as maltodextrin [26], which is one of the most common excipients used within spray drying processes [25].

3.2. Water solubility index (WSI)

WSI is the ability of a powder to be dissolved in water [9]. Unlike hygroscopicity and moisture content, high WSI values are desirable. There is an inverse correlation between WSI and moisture content as lower moisture content facilitates fast solubilisation [29]. The WSI for all tested biocoagulants here exceeded 60 % regardless of storage time and conditions. However, higher WSI values were observed for powders originating from salt extracts (with maximum values of 90.2 and 92.7 % for KNO and UNO biocoagulants, respectively) compared to powder coagulants originating from water extracts (maximum values of 78.1 and 69.4 % for KVO and UVO biocoagulants, respectively) (Fig. 3). Hence, in this respect, the KNO and UNO biocoagulants were advantageous in comparison to the KVO and UVO coagulants. In comparison to other studies, the WSIs of common bean powder coagulants here were comparable to those of other lyophilised biocoagulants. For instance, the solubility of lyophilised *Moringa oleifera* was 73.89 %, similar to raw, natural, *Moringa oleifera* powder (74.03 %) [12]. Slightly lower water solubility was observed for lyophilised *Hibiscus sabdariffa* coagulant

Fig. 2. Hygroscopicity of 4 common bean seed powdered biocoagulants (sampling frequency: 12 h, 1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 days; powdered biocoagulant mass: 1 g; relative humidity: 70 %).

Fig. 3. Water solubility index (WSI) values for all 4 coagulants, at the beginning of the investigated period (0 time), after 4 months in controlled conditions (CC) and after 3 months in non-controlled conditions (NCC) (powdered biocoagulant mass: 1.5 g; water volume: 15 mL; incubation temperature: 30 °C; incubation time: 30 min; centrifugation speed: 3000 rpm; centrifugation time: 15 min).

(40–57 %, depending on the powder concentration (20 and 30 wt%) and freeze-drying durations (24 and 65 h)) [16]. Spray dried tomato powder showed low water solubility (17.65 to 26.73 %) attributed to its low sugar content compared to most other fruits, and higher content of liposoluble substances such as carotenoids [29]. These results were comparable to those obtained for a powder from ginger juice lyophilised without the addition of a carrier material [22]. However, WSI values were notably enhanced (up to 96 %) by the addition of a carrier material (maltodextrin and lipid glucose) before drying [22].

Theoretically, as stated in Zheng et al. (2021), a high WSI is related to high powder porosity. Hence, it could be suggested that KNO and UNO biocoagulants have higher porosity than KVO and UVO biocoagulants. However, this assumption should be instrumentally tested and verified, before making final conclusions. Additionally, powders with higher WSIs should have better coagulation performances [16]. Based on these assumptions, the UNO biocoagulant would be the preferable option for utilisation in water treatment.

3.3. Moisture and dry matter content

One of the major factors affecting the stability of a powder is water (moisture) content [9]. Similar to hygroscopicity, high moisture content is undesirable, as a humid environment facilitates microbiological activity, which leads to decreased powder shelf life. Additionally, a high moisture content can facilitate caking [24]. Generally, desirable moisture contents in powdered products are 3 to 5 % [30] and products with moisture contents <5 % could be classified as microbiologically safe and can be stored for longer periods [24]. Here, although biocoagulants extracted with distilled water did not exceed that value drastically (KVO and UVO coagulants had moisture contents between 6 and 7 %, which was similar to the spray dried tomato powders obtained by Santos de Sousa et al. (2008)), biocoagulants originating from salt extracts showed better results (moisture contents of KNO and UNO coagulants were near 3 %) (Fig. 4).

Table 2 shows the dry matter content results for liquid coagulant extracts. Higher dry matters of salt extracts (KNO and UNO) in comparison to distilled water extracts are in compliance with previous findings [15]. Salt extraction predominance comes from the fact that salt

Fig. 4. Moisture (a) and dry matter content (b) of all 4 powdered coagulants, at the beginning of the investigated period (0 time), and after storage for 4 months in controlled conditions (CC) and 3 months in non-controlled conditions (NCC) (sample volume: 5 mL; drying time: 2.5 h; drying temperature: 105 °C).

solutions enhance the extraction process by breaking-down protein-protein bonds. By breaking bonds in herbal materials, higher amounts of active components are extracted [6,20]. Some drying techniques are not justified for extracts with dry matter contents below a certain value. Low dry matter contents in liquid extracts results in low drying yields, hence, the consumption of excess energy to produce small amounts of powder - which is not economically justified. In this context, KVO and UVO extracts, obtained with distilled water as the solvent, should preferably be dried by freeze-drying. To achieve a more cost-effective drying process

in such cases, extracts could be concentrated and/or different carrier materials could be added into the feed [24].

3.4. Jar-test experiments

The efficiency of the 4 biocoagulants (KVO, KNO, UVO and UNO) when kept in controlled and non-controlled conditions was tested in terms of turbidity removal from model water (with initial conditions of 200 NTU and pH 6). The initial turbidity and pH values were chosen

Fig. 5. Coagulation efficiency (turbidity removal) for 4 powder coagulants kept in controlled conditions for up to 4 months (biocoagulant dosage: 0.05–1.5, (2, 2.5), mL/L; fast mixing: 200 rpm for 1 min, slow mixing: 60 rpm for 30 min, settling: 1 h; initial pH 6; initial turbidity: 200 NTU).

based on previous results achieved for liquid extracts of the same bio-coagulants (prior to the lyophilisation step) [31]. Alnawajha et al. (2022) emphasised in their review that changes in pH caused by bio-coagulants may present one important drawback for implementation in real systems [32]. Hence, the pH of the final model solution was measured in order to establish the influence of the coagulant on the pH value of the treated water.

Evaluation of coagulation efficiency revealed that all bio-coagulants achieved high maximal turbidity removal (>50 and up to 80.2 %), which is comparable to previously tested liquid (crude) extracts of the same material [31]. Optimal coagulant dosages varied (from 0.2 to 1 mL/L) through time and based on storage conditions, but with no observed specific pattern (Figs. 5 and 6). Furthermore, maximal coagulation efficiencies varied irregularly through the investigated time period, i.e., without a clear trend (Table 3). Maximal coagulation activity achieved by KVO and KNO crude extracts were 58.4 (optimal dosage: 0.1 mL/L) and 83.5 % (optimal dosage: 0.4 mL/L) [31], while UVO and UNO crude extracts achieved maximal coagulation activity of 82.4 (optimal dosage: 0.5 mL/L) and 85.7 % (optimal dosage: 0.2 mL/L), respectively (Fig. 7). Some bio-coagulants showed better performance after storage than immediately after production (e.g., the UNO coagulant had a CA of 53.2 % before storage, whilst after two months of storage this increased to 80.1 %) (Table 3). Similar results were observed by Katayon et al. (2006) who investigated turbidity removal using non-freeze dried *Moringa oleifera* coagulants over 12 months of storage. Therein, coagulation efficiency notably decreased after the first month of storage (from >90 % to 0 %), but then increased again over time, especially between the ninth and twelfth month (by around 20 %). This phenomena was attributed to a slight reduction in pH (from 6.2 to 5.4), probably due to the presence of organic acids produced by microbial decomposition of organic compounds within plant seeds [8]. In contrast, freeze-dried *Moringa oleifera* bio-coagulants from the same study retained

high turbidity removal over time (70–94.3 %) [8]. Coagulation efficiencies here (50.6 to 80.2 %) and corresponding coefficients of variation (<20 %) were in accordance with the results achieved for freeze-dried (rather than non-freeze-dried) bio-coagulants used in the study of Katayon et al. (2006). Hence, differences in coagulation performance (Table 3) might be attributed to different contents of active components in common bean seeds and their heterogeneous distribution within liquid extracts and the consequently produced powders.

All 4 tested bio-coagulants showed no influence on the pH of treated model waters, which remained the same (~6) after the jar tests. This is highly beneficial from both an ecological and economical aspect as there is then no need for additional chemicals for pH adjustment. Very acidic or very basic conditions in treatment systems and in effluents are undesirable, hence, maintaining a pH near neutral is of great value.

As can be seen from Table 3, maximum CAs for bio-coagulants kept in controlled and non-controlled conditions were very similar: 66.0 and 67.6 % for KVO, 80.0 and 77.4 % for KNO, 70.7 and 73.0 % for UVO and 80.1 and 78.0 % for UNO (respectively). Based on this, it could be concluded that storage conditions did not notably affect the CAs, which is positive from a commercialisation aspect, since these powdered coagulants then do not require special storage conditions to maintain their coagulation properties. CAs at time point zero (before storage) were excluded from the previous comparison since they do not reflect the influence of storage conditions. Furthermore, it should be noted that maximal CAs were sometimes achieved under different optimal coagulant doses, which should be considered when drawing conclusions and making comparisons between bio-coagulant types. However, higher maximal CAs were (in certain cases) achieved by application of lower doses of bio-coagulant kept in non-controlled conditions versus a bio-coagulant kept in controlled conditions. The UVO bio-coagulant presents the best choice due to its consistency in optimal coagulant dosage (1 mL/L) and maximal CA (64.4 to 80.2 %). Consistent behaviour of an applied

Fig. 6. Coagulation efficiency (turbidity removal) for 4 powder coagulants kept in non-controlled conditions for up to 6 months (bio-coagulant dosage: 0.05–1.5, (2, 2.5), mL/L; fast mixing: 200 rpm for 1 min, slow mixing: 60 rpm for 30 min, settling: 1 h; initial pH 6; initial turbidity: 200 NTU).

Table 3

Maximum coagulation efficiencies (CA) and corresponding coagulant dosages (turbidity removal) for 4 tested coagulants stored in controlled and non-controlled conditions.

Storage time (months)	Controlled conditions						Non-controlled conditions							
	0		2		4		0		1.5		3		6	
Coagulant type	Max CA (%)	Applied coagulant dosage (mL/L)	Max CA (%)	Applied coagulant dosage (mL/L)	Max CA (%)	Applied coagulant dosage (mL/L)	Max CA (%)	Applied coagulant dosage (mL/L)	Max CA (%)	Applied coagulant dosage (mL/L)	Max CA (%)	Applied coagulant dosage (mL/L)	Max CA (%)	Applied coagulant dosage (mL/L)
KVO	52.7 %	0.4	66.0 %	0.5	61.7 %	0.5	52.7 %	0.4	50.6 %	1	67.6 %	0.4	54.6 %	1
KNO	70.1 %	1	80.0 %	0.3	69.3 %	0.3	70.1 %	1	73.8 %	1	59.0 %	1	77.4 %	0.4
UVO	80.2 %	1	65.3 %	1	70.7 %	1	80.2 %	1	72.4 %	1	73.0 %	1	64.4 %	1
UNO	53.1 %	1	80.1 %	1	67.7 %	0.5	53.2 %	1	77.3 %	0.4	69.0 %	0.5	78.0 %	0.2

Fig. 7. Coagulation efficiency (turbidity removal) for UVO and UNO crude extracts (biocoagulant dosage: 0.2–0.6 mL/L; fast mixing: 200 rpm for 1 min, slow mixing: 60 rpm for 30 min, settling: 1 h; initial pH 6; initial turbidity: 200 NTU).

biocoagulant is very important for real world applications in water or wastewater treatment - wherein this would result in good predictions for coagulant behaviour and efficiency for a selected purpose under specified conditions.

Results concerning organic matter (OM) removal by biocoagulants confirmed (Fig. 8) assumptions that the addition of biocoagulants of organic nature will lead to an increase in organic matter content in the treated model water as a coagulant purification step was not implemented within the production process. All tested biocoagulants (regardless of storage time and storage conditions) showed an increase in organic matter content in treated model waters. Although chemical composition of powdered coagulants was not specifically evaluated

through current work, powdered coagulants were obtained from the crude extracts of common bean whose chemical composition is already well known (Supplementary data, Table S1) [31]. Additionally, Table S2 of Supplementary data shows chemical composition of KVO and KNO crude extracts [33].

There is an obvious correlation between applied biocoagulant dose and an increase in organic matter content. Purification of a common bean biocoagulant was previously tested by Antov et al. (2012) and this showed promising results in the reduction of organic load that remained after coagulation (in comparison to crude extracts). The problem with increased organic matter was also observed when treating lake water. After addition of 1 mL/L of biocoagulant, COD levels increased by 25 %.

Fig. 8. Coagulation efficiency based on organic matter removal (CA_{COD} (%)) of UVO coagulant kept in non-controlled conditions using a model water (a) and meat processing effluent (b). Biocoagulant dose in model water: 0.05–1.5, mL/L, biocoagulant dose in EMCI: 0.1, 1 and 1.5, mL/L; fast mixing: 200 rpm for 1 min, slow mixing: 60 rpm for 30 min, settling: 1 h; model water pH 6, model water initial turbidity: 200 NTU; EMCI pH 2, EMCI initial turbidity: 256, EMCI COD: 2705.

In contrast, biocoagulant showed promising results for COD reduction in industrial effluents (Fig. 9).

Based on these results, it could be concluded that crude biocoagulant extracts are not suitable for the treatment of relatively pure water and for conditioning of drinking water. In this case, the biocoagulant should be purified first. However, a biocoagulant without purification could be efficiently used for the treatment of highly loaded wastewater where it can lead to notable COD reduction.

3.5. Characterisation of the UVO coagulant

SEM analysis revealed morphologically heterogeneous surface, consisted of sheets of different shape and size (Fig. 10a and b). Specific SEM images (Fig. 10c, d and e) showed that the C and O elements appear on the same sites of the biocoagulant, confirming bonds between C and O at the UVO surface (as showed within FTIR spectra- Fig. 11a). K (which is present to the lower extent on the UVO surface), was additionally detected, on independent UVO surface sites, which was expected due to the fact that bean seeds contain potassium as an essential mineral for human body.

Fig. 9. Organic matter removal from different aquatic matrixes (LW, WDE and EMCI). UVO coagulant dose: 1 mL/L; fast mixing: 200 rpm for 1 min, slow mixing: 60 rpm for 30 min, settling: 1 h; LW pH 7.3, LW initial turbidity: 4.3 NTU, LW initial COD: 27.1; WDE pH 3.9, WDE initial turbidity: 9400 NTU, WDE initial COD: 150; EMCI pH 2, EMCI initial turbidity: 256, EMCI COD: 2705.

Fig. 10. FESEM (a, b, c, d, e) micrographs and EDX spectra (f) of UVO coagulant.

Fig. 11. FTIR spectrum (a), XRD pattern (b) and XPS spectra (c, d, e) of UVO biocoagulant.

The EDX surface spectra (Fig. 10f) of UVO biocoagulant indicated that C was the major element, alongside O and N, which was expected due to the organic nature of obtained biocoagulants, containing proteins and polysaccharides as major chemical components (Tables S1 and S2).

Obtained FTIR spectra of UVO coagulant revealed peaks comparable to ones of the biocoagulant from prickly pear peel waste investigated by

[34]. As it can be seen from Fig. 11a, there were several peaks indicating characteristic functional groups present at biocoagulant surface. Peak observed at 3243 cm^{-1} is associated with the stretching vibration of the hydroxyl group bonds (O—H), which could be attributed to the polysaccharide structure of biocoagulants and presence of galacturonic acid. Besides proteins, polysaccharides have coagulation ability, which may

contribute to the overall coagulation ability of UVO coagulant. The peak at 1601 cm^{-1} additionally indicates polysaccharides in biocoagulant due to the presence of the stretching of the C=O bond, which is characteristic of a carboxyl group. Moreover, the peaks around 1400 cm^{-1} indicate uronic acid in the polysaccharide molecule [34]. Peaks around 1649 cm^{-1} and 1536 cm^{-1} , as reported in the biocoagulants from *Cocos nucifera* [35] and *Moringa oleifera* [36], correspond to the C=O in primary and secondary amides of proteins and could also be observed in the FTIR spectra of UVO biocoagulant. Based on the results from the FTIR spectra, it could be concluded that proteins and the polysaccharides were the dominant species of UVO biocoagulant having coagulation ability and consequently removing turbidity from water.

The XRD patterns of the UVO sample shown a pattern of a flat background with the bands of low intensities, emphasised the amorphous nature of the biocoagulant (Fig. 11b). The diffraction pattern of the biomass showed peaks located at 2θ between 18° and 22° which could be ascribed to the (002) plane of native cellulose lattice.

The further elemental composition for UVO was obtained from XPS survey scan. As shown in Fig. 11c, the mass fractions of C, O and N were determined to be 71.44 %, 21.34 % and 6.17 %, respectively. K and P were present in much lower mass fractions (<1 %) compared to C, O and N. High-resolution XPS spectra of C 1s and O 1s were deconvoluted to gain information about the surface functional groups of UVO. There were three C 1s peaks in Fig. 11d. The peak at 284.9 eV was assigned to a C–C and C–H bonds; the peak at 286.1 eV was attributed to a C–OH or C–O bond; and the peak at 288.2 eV was related with a C=O bond from a carboxylate carbonyl group [37]. The O 1s peak at 531.9 eV assigned to O=C – O bond, while the peak at 532.8 eV was attributed to the C–OH group (Fig. 11e) [38]. These results further confirmed the abundance of carboxyl and hydroxyl groups in its structure of polysaccharides and proteins, which were responsible for the biocoagulant activity. Similar results were reported in the study by Liu et al. [39].

4. Conclusion

Based on these results, biocoagulants from common bean seeds possess promising commercial value. Based on maximal coagulation activities (up to 80.2 %), moisture contents (lower than 7 %) and good water solubility (always higher than 60 % and going up to 92.7 %) in excess over several months of storage, there is clear evidence that these biocoagulants will maintain their physico-chemical properties over long periods of time, which is of high importance for future commercialisation. Another important finding which facilitates common bean powder coagulant commercialisation is that no special storage conditions were required (there were negligible fluctuations in properties of coagulants kept in controlled and non-controlled conditions) within the investigated period of time. From all tested biocoagulant, not only that UVO coagulant showed the highest coagulation activity (80.2 %), but it also had the best consistency within obtained results (optimal dosage was always 1 mL/L for all tested conditions and times), which is also highly important for future real-scale utilisation. Experiments using real industrial effluents showed that the produced biocoagulants could be efficiently used for COD reduction in highly loaded wastewaters (COD reduction of almost 50 % achieved in industrial effluents). Although these coagulants showed promising results, further steps, including production scale-up, should be taken before their final placement on the market.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Sanja Cojbasic: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Maja Turk Sekulic:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Sabolec Pap:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Mark A. Taggart:** Writing – review & editing. **Jelena Prodanovic:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jwpe.2024.105863>.

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